

Traces

Memories - Emotions - Stories – Objects

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Abstract: How can a new craft object be emotionally compelling? How can other people's memory stories inspire an artist to create an object and make it evocative? This is a working paper exploring the literature from various disciplines concerning memory, emotion and objects. The approach links intersecting elements to frame a research methodology applicable to craft making for bespoke narrative artifacts. Critical issues include defining memory for purposes of the research and devising methods to tap into emotive memories. Ongoing research is refining the memory cuing methods and devising strategies for interpreting memories into object form. The aim is to devise new pathways to the creation of evocative artifacts that connect owners of the objects to revered memories and traces of identity.

Key words: *Craft and emotion; autobiographical memory; evocative objects; storytelling.*

1. Introduction

This practice-based research project explores an alternative conceptual basis for making narrative craft artifacts. Unlike other design disciplines, a user-centered approach is not the norm for narrative craft objects. More frequently, the artist's/maker's (artist) motivation draws from personal experience. In this alternative scenario the future owner of a new artifact is a 'sitter'. The artist creates a new object, akin to a 'portrait', revealing something of the essence of the sitter. The sessions between sitter and artist engage the former in 'personal memory telling'. The sitter's memory stories become the features inspiring the artist.

The ultimate aim is to develop a working methodology to create narrative artifacts that are evocative for sitters. The objects will reflect either a prototypical story or an amalgamation of accounts that illuminate repeated patterns of character. The stories will drive the nature and type of artifact produced. They will determine the object's qualities: scale, form, material, intimacy and functionality – whether utilitarian (adornment, vessels) or purely contemplative (sculptural), always reinforcing identity.

This paper provides an outline of the links between autobiographical memory, emotion and objects that underpin the project's methodology. It also suggests a framework for memory cuing methods. Ongoing research is developing and testing the methods, transforming sitters' stories into objects. It is also exploring the

application of the methodologies to collective memory situations, enabling eventual community-based projects or more universally applicable object creation.

2. Underlying Theories

2.1. Autobiographical Memory Stories

The theoretical foundation rooting this project is Schank and Abelson's (1995) model for human memory. They identify memory as a collection of stories – experienced, conveyed, or composed. Throughout development we create scripts: dynamic frameworks into which existing memories can be collected and new memories collated.^[1] Story-based memory is critical for our sense of self. The stories we devise shape our self-concept.^[2] This memory delineation is known as autobiographical memory: memory for significant stories linked to identity, lasting our lifetime and available to narrative recall.^[3] Autobiographical memory stories are remembered because they are retold. Memory retrieval is managed via story indexing: links or cues are layered onto the structure of the stories, which fosters recollection. Often the objects in our lives act as fundamental memory story triggers.

2.2. Objects and Memory

Studies in material culture connect objects to autobiographical memory and storytelling by examining the cultural artifacts that compose our lives. Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981) demonstrated that even mundane household objects acquire emotional significance, usually related to their ability to trigger memories.^[4] Subsequently, Belk (1988) presented a compelling case for objects as an extension of self. Identity is reinforced when cherished yet everyday possessions hold significant memories, whether from actual association with particular situations or through nostalgia for the past.^[5] Turkle (2007) described such extraordinary 'ordinary' objects as evocative by their ability to connect us with some part of our lives: childhood, life transitions or relationships, i.e. to autobiographical memory.^[6]

An object made by an artist can carry its own inherent evocative qualities. Walther Benjamin (1936 in Leslie, 1998) links the making of objects with storytelling and memory. He suggests that a storyteller's recitations expose traces of personality just as the ceramicist's pot reveals the maker's hand: both leave tacit memory traces.^[7] In this project, memory traces embedded in the new object are inspired by the storyteller (sitter) and must be meaningful to them. However the artist's voice, via their interpretations and creation, their hand, are vital to the new object's intrinsic value and authenticity.

If emotionally charged objects embedded with stories are comparable to props in our personal life scripts, then the objects created in this project should be new props enhancing the sitters' lives.

2.3. Collective Unconscious and Storytelling

Storytelling functions from a collective as well as an individual perspective. Indeed, storytelling via literary fairy tales, oral narratives or social histories is fundamental to the transmission of cultural priorities. Jung interpreted myths and cultural storytelling, via archetypes from our collective unconscious, as critical to identity

formation.^[8] Anthropologists and archaeologists associate collective storytelling and archetypal imagery to objects within the society that transmit a culture's stories. These heirlooms are objects that transmit significant cultural and societal stories to the next generation. They become receptacles of a culture's collective memory, embedding the stories of prior generations and embellishing identity. As such, they contribute to our autobiographical memory.^[9] This project aims to create personal heirlooms.

2.4. Emotions and Memory

Autobiographical memory is dynamic, with emotion as a primary variable. Studies reveal interaction in the brain's limbic system between the amygdala (processing emotion) and hippocampal regions (memory retrieval and retention). Emotionally significant events are more entrenched in our memory than neutral events and more available to recall.^[10] The ability to reconnect to emotionally charged autobiographical memories is influenced both by the emotional context of the memory and the retrieval situation.^[11]

3. Sitter's Memory Retrieval

3.1. Memory Cues and The Retrieval Context

This project is testing methods to elicit autobiographical memory stories that reveal emotional priorities and character, just as prior HCI research developed 'cultural probes' to learn more about the personal habits of end-users.^[12] The methods at issue require finding triggers that are emotionally evocative and tap into a sitter's memory story index. The testing must take place in an emotionally safe recall environment. Recent fMRI studies of the limbic system reveal the neurological link between sensory (e.g. olfactory or auditory) associations and emotionally laden memories, as foreshadowed by Proust (1913).^[13] Drawing upon the effectiveness of sensory cues, diverse sensory stimuli and associations with place and time will be tested as triggers in both spontaneous and reflective conditions whilst also insuring the sitter is at ease. Hence, the relationship between the artist and sitter is critical: in spontaneous memory cuing situations, the artist is present as an active listener; a reflective context has the sitter respond to triggers over time via a personal memory story journal.

3.2. Outcomes

The end-goal is a transformation from textual memory story to object creation. Repeated threads and patterns in the sitter's stories will be analyzed and interpreted via symbols, metaphor and metonymy into object form, endowing unique meaning. Or, the new object may be reflective of a prototypical story. The new artifact's composition, form, texture, material composition and purpose are all relevant interpretive elements at the design stage. This phase will engage a semiotic analysis of the story elements by looking at personalized symbols.^[14] The object must be meaningful to the sitter. Whether the object resonates with the sitter is the litmus test for the methods as well as the artist's interpretation.

4. Conclusion

The existing literature demonstrates the storytelling nature of autobiographical memory and the role of evocative objects in reinforcing identity. This project applies these theories and in the testing phase is investigating various sensory-based cuing methods to retrieve memory stories from sitters as inspiration for future artifacts. A dialogue between artist and sitter engages these methods and supports the storytelling process. The outcomes involve

interpreting stories into a narrative object that is evocative for the sitter. Ongoing research is examining universal motifs excavated by personal storytelling, exploring the application of the methodologies to collective memory situations that will enable more widely relevant object creation.

In this paradigm, storytelling is key – it is the source of the memories, the objective of the memory cuing and the design outcome via narrative works. If the research is successful, the evocative objects produced will all be purposeful: they will be memento vitae for the sitters, future heirlooms that trigger memories reinforcing their character and aspirations.

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